
A Study of knowledge of Income Tax Act 1961 amongst the people of Maharashtra State

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Abstract:

In India first time Sir James Wilson was introduced Tax in the year 1860 where decided to impose it to meet the amount of losses sustained by the government due to Sepoy Mutiny, 1857. After some years, in 1918 a new income tax Act was introduced but it was replaced by another new Act which was passed in 1922. This is the long term Act remained in force to the year 1961-62. On the recommendations of Prof. Nicholas Kaldor, the Wealth Tax Act, 1957, the Expenditure Tax Act, 1957 and Gift Tax Act, 1958 were introduced. In the year 1958, a report on new Income Tax Act was submitted by the Law Commission and based on these recommendations, Income-tax Act, 1961 came into force with effect from 1st of April, 1962. Since 1962 to upto date, several amendments regarding exemption, tax slab, allowance have been made every year through the Union Budget. Now, it has become a regular feature to present the Finance Bill every year along with Union Budget that include rates of income tax for the next year.

The researchers have used primary data for the research work. The primary data has been collected by conducting surveys through structural questionnaire from 383 respondents i.e. students, salary persons and research students from Maharashtra. The sample population is selected by using random sampling techniques.

Introduction:

In India first time Sir James Wilson was introduced Tax in the year 1860 where decided to impose it to meet the amount of losses sustained by the government due to Sepoy Mutiny, 1857. After some years, in 1918 a new income tax Act was introduced but it was replaced by another new Act which was passed in 1922. This is the long term Act remained in force to the year 1961-62. On the recommendations of Prof. Nicholas Kaldor, the Wealth Tax Act, 1957, the Expenditure Tax Act, 1957 and Gift Tax Act, 1958 were introduced. In the year 1958, a report on new Income Tax Act was submitted by the Law Commission and based on these recommendations, Income-

tax Act, 1961 came into force with effect from 1st of April, 1962. Since 1962 to upto date, several amendments regarding exemption, tax slab, allowance have been made every year through the Union Budget. Now, it has become a regular feature to present the Finance Bill every year along with Union Budget that include rates of income tax for the next year.

Income Tax Act 1962 in the Section 14, there are five main heads of income for any person. The computation of income tax is an important part and has to be calculated according to the income of a person for easily calculation. The income has to be classified properly so that there is no confusion regarding the calculations. The

Income tax Act 1961 and amendments were classified the sources of income under separate heads and then the income tax is computed accordingly. The provisions and rules are according to the details mentioned in the Income Tax Act 1961. In this research we try to study the knowledge of the salaries persons, and students about the Income Tax Act 1961 and its amendments.

Objective of the Study:

1. To study the knowledge of Income Tax Act 1961 and its important concepts.
2. To know the knowledge of calculation of Income Tax.
3. To study the information about exemptions under Income Tax Act 1961.

Research Methodology:

The researchers have used primary data for the research work. The primary data has been collected by conducting surveys through structural questionnaire from 383 respondents i.e. students, salary persons and research students from Maharashtra. The sample population is selected by using random sampling techniques.

Data Analysis:

The data was collected through oral interview and structural questionnaire in Google form from students, research students and college teachers.

Table No. 1: Category wise Information of sample collected

Sr. No.	Category	No	Percentage (% to Total)
1.	Professor	16	4.2%
2.	Associate Professor	20	5.2%
3.	Assistant Professor	118	30.8%
4.	Research Scholar	34	8.9%
5.	Students	194	50.7

Source: Survey

It is observed from the above table 50.7% of students, 8.9% research students and 40.2% college teacher were given the responses for the study.

In the Income Tax Act 1961, various concepts that were being used in various places of the Act. Unless these concepts are

understood in its totality, the knowledge about the income tax will not be complete. These concepts were clear to the people or not for these purpose some of question asked to the people by the researcher. The following data was collected

Table No. 2: The table showing the knowledge of basic concepts as per Income Tax Act 1961

Sr. No.	Particular	Knowledge of Basic Concept	Percentage (% to Total)
1.	Concept	317	82.55%
2.	Type of Taxes	306	79.68%
3.	Income of Government	354	92.18%
4.	Assesses/Person	276	71.87%

Source: Survey

From the above table it is observed that many of the people having the knowledge about the basic concept i.e. meaning of income 82.55%, types of taxes

79.68%, Income of a Government 92.18% and assesses 71.87%.

It is also important that the people not only know about the important basic

but also the types of income and minimum exemption for these purpose we asked

some question and following data was collected

Table No. 3: The table showing the knowledge of types of income & exemptions as per Income Tax Act 1961

Sr. No.	Particular	Numbers	Percentage (% to Total)
1.	Income Exemption for tax	306	79.68%
2.	Exemption under 80c	269	70.05%
3.	Income from Salary	326	84.89%
4.	Income from House Property	325	84.90%
5.	Income from Capital Gain	230	59.90%
6.	Income from other sources	320	83.33%

Source: Survey

It is observed from table no. 3 the knowledge of the types of income and exemptions as per Income Tax Act 1961 as per the data 75% people were know about the exemption of income tax and 80% people were having the knowledge of types of income.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that the major of the people having the information about basic concept i.e. 78% (Table No. 2 and 70% were knowledge of types of income and basic exemption. It is useful them to calculate their taxable income.

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